

FATIGUE FROM WATERHAMMER ON FILAMENT WOUND GRE-PIPES AND ADHESIVE BONDED JOINTS.

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an investigation which addresses the problem of fatigue caused by water hammer in glass-fibre reinforced epoxy (GRE) pipes jointed by adhesive bonded couplers. A test method was established using a new-developed servo-hydraulic test rig. The fatigue life of the test specimens are presented as a P-N curve, and the failure mechanisms are characterized by splitting the test specimens for closer investigation of the crack paths in a microscope. Acoustic emission measurements were performed in order to determine the initiation and propagation of cracks.

Keywords: Glass-fibre Reinforced Epoxy, GRE, pipes, water hammer fatigue, fatigue testing, acoustic emission.

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass-fibre reinforced plastic (GRP) materials have received increased attention within the North Sea offshore industry during the last 5-7 years. In many applications, GRP provides good corrosion resistance, low weight, long service life, low maintenance costs and faster and easier installation compared to traditional metallic materials. Factors which have restricted more extensive use of these materials have been concern about the fire hazard and lack of documentation on material properties relevant for offshore loadings. The Norwegian Petroleum Directorate (NPD) has focused on several areas where more knowledge and documentation is needed, and the effects of water hammer in GRP-pipes is one of these.

Water flowing through a pipe bears energy. Part of this energy is kinetic due to velocity, part is potential, as a result of pressure. The sum of these two energies (ignoring friction losses) remains constant throughout the piping system. Simply explained, whenever the velocity changes there is a change in the kinetic energy. Since the system does not essentially gain or lose energy, a compensating change occurs in the potential energy, with a corresponding change in pressure. This pressure increase produces pressure waves which travel through the pipe and fluid system at sonic velocities. This effect is designated water hammer, and has the character of pressure pulsation. Its intensity, evidenced as a surge in pressure, depends among other things upon the rate with which the velocity is altered. Typical examples of conditions that can generate water hammer are the operation of valves, the starting and stopping of pumps, recombination after water-column separation etc. For

a general introduction to transients in piping systems the reader is referred to reviews by Streeter and Wylie [1, 2] and Fox [3].

There have been several studies to investigate both the fatigue life of polymer composites and the specific impact characteristics [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and references therein]. The present investigation concentrates on the determination of fatigue from water hammer on filament-wound glass-fibre reinforced epoxy (GRE) pipes and adhesive bonded pipe joints. GRE-pipes and couplers commonly used in offshore applications were selected for the test programme. The biaxial loading, which is obtained by using a test rig built for the purpose (as described later), simulates realistic loading conditions when GRE pipes are subjected to water hammer in order to introduce realistic failure modes in the test specimens.

2. WATER HAMMER CHARACTERISTICS

For a sudden velocity change, maximum pressure increase can be calculated by Equation 1 given by Wylie and Streeter [2]:

$$\Delta p_i = -\rho a \Delta v \left(1 + \frac{v_0}{a}\right) \quad (1)$$

where Δp_i denotes the pressure increase, ρ the density of the process fluid, a the water hammer wave velocity in the pipe, Δv the change in fluid velocity and v_0 denotes the initial fluid velocity.

The theory for the calculation of water hammer wave velocities is described in [2], but only with reference to isotropic materials. Based upon the same theory, the equation for GRE-pipes can be derived which gives Equation 2:

$$a = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{K}{\rho}}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{K d}{E_t e} c_1}} \quad (2)$$

where K denotes the bulk modulus of elasticity of the process fluid, d is the inside diameter of the pipe, E_t is the tangential modulus of elasticity, e is the pipe wall thickness and c_1 is a function of both Poisson's ratio for the pipe material and the restraint of the pipe. The three most common support situations gives the following values for c_1 (in subscript ta and at , axial/hoop respectively hoop/axial, the first index gives the direction of contraction and the second index gives the load direction):

- (a) pipe anchored at its upstream end only: $c_1 = 1 - \frac{v_{ta}}{2}$
- (b) pipe anchored throughout against axial movement: $c_1 = 1 - v_{at} v_{ta}$
- (c) pipe anchored with expansion joints throughout: $c_1 = 1$

Equation 2 is based on the assumption that the modulus of elasticity of the material and the liquid are constant over the range of strains occurring. Furthermore, the material must be rigid, so that the changes in pipe volume under pressure fluctuations are very small. Equation 1 is confirmed by several experiments [9 and references therein], while Equation 2 is confirmed in the case of isotropic materials.

With regard to water hammer caused by valves, maximum pressure increase is obtained when the valve is completely closed before the pressure wave has travelled the distance from the valve to the reservoir and back, $2L$. This time is called the critical closing time and is given by Equation 3:

$$t_{cr} = \frac{2L}{a} \quad (3)$$

The pressure wave is a square-like wave and its duration is given by Equation 4:

$$t_{puls} = \frac{4L}{a} \quad (4)$$

Due to friction and non-elastic deformation, the pressure wave will decrease in amplitude as it travels along the pipe line.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Test specimens

The test method was developed by running a preliminary test programme on straight pipes. As joints are expected to be the weakest points in a GRE-piping system, the main test programme was concentrated on these parts.

A total of 25 tubular test specimens were fabricated for the main test programme. Each test specimen consisted of two GRE-pipes jointed with a coupler as shown in Figure 1. The jointing operation was performed in compliance with the pipe producer's specification. For some of the test specimens, a deviation from the postcuring specification (1 hour at 130°C) was made to study the consequences of undercure, i.e. no postcure. The specimen data are summarized in Table 1.

3.2 Test equipment

The GRE-pipes were tested under internal impact biaxial loading conditions. In order to simulate water hammer, square-like pressure waves were generated and led into the water-filled pipe by using a servo-hydraulic test rig with an INSTRON Model 2165 controller. The complete test rig is shown schematically in Figure 2. The apparatus consists basically of two individual self-clamping end couplings in which the upper coupling is integrated with a cylinder. A piston driven by the servo-hydraulic test machine generates pressure waves with a selected rise time, duration and amplitude. For safety reasons, the piston contains a hole for deaeration before start-up.

The acoustic emission measurements were performed with a four channel PAC 3401. Two PAC R50D sensors were fastened to the GRE-coupler, while two PAC WD were used as guard sensors fastened to the GRE-pipe close to the end couplings, see Figure 2. The equipment was calibrated according to guidelines in [10].

3.3 Test method

General guidelines for S-N characterisation of composite materials are given in [8]. Constant amplitude fatigue tests are normally conducted under three to five different stress levels, where the extreme stress levels are approximately chosen so that the number of fatigue cycles ends up somewhere between 10^4 and 10^6 .

The load cycle for the fatigue test was selected so that the rise time up to 90 % of maximal load was between 50 to 80 milliseconds. (depending on the maximum load level), and the duration at maximum load was set to approximately 500 milliseconds. This value corresponds to the calculated duration for a 100 m long GRE-pipeline.

The test was run in load control with the function generator set to produce square waves with a frequency of 1 Hz. An oscilloscope recorded the load signal in order to check that the wave parameters were in accordance with desired values. The number of cycles was registered by means of a cycle counter. In the beginning of the test programme, the loading cycle was measured both with the load signal and separately with a Kisteler pressure transducer which was fastened to the lower end-coupling. Very good agreement between load versus time could be observed for the two sensors, see Figure 3. The two signals were, in this case, recorded using a data acquisition module attached to a PC. For the remaining tests, only the load signal was used to measure the pressure.

Strain gauges for both axial and hoop strain were used during the preliminary test programme to compare calculated and measured strain in the GRE-pipe during loading. The strain and load curve followed the same path, and the difference between calculated and measured values was within acceptable limits.

Acoustic emission measurements were performed to evaluate if the method could provide a measure of the degree of damage development in the test specimens during fatigue cycling. Two acoustic emission techniques [10] were investigated; (1) by continuous accumulation of the total number of counts and (2) by measuring the Felicity ratio, defined as the ratio between load at onset of emission and the maximum prior load, i.e. the test pressure, at specific intervals during test run.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The maximum permitted flow rate for water in GRE-pipes is normally 5 m/sec. By applying the data from Table 1 to Equation 1, 2 and 4, it can be seen that a sudden reduction in the flow rate from 5 m/sec. to 0 m/sec. will lead to a pressure increase of 2.6 MPa. This pressure increase is overlaid the normal service pressure, which for the tested pipe specimens is limited to 2.5 MPa, so that the total pressure amounts to 5.1 MPa.

Available experimental results seem to support the assumption that the adhesive bonded coupler joint is weaker than the GRE-pipe itself. The results reported below show that it is possible to establish a P-N diagram with an acceptable confidence interval for adhesive bonded GRE-pipes subjected to water hammer.

4.1 Fatigue life

Based upon the pipe-producer's stress criteria and the axial and tangential stresses calculated by the simple thin walled pressure vessel formula, the safety factor (S_f) for each load level can be calculated. S_f is reduced from 1.95 for the lowest load level, to 1.35 for the highest load level.

A leakage rate of about 10 mm³/cycle was used as a criterion for the fatigue life, and the data from fatigue testing are plotted in a P-N diagram, Figure 4. As can be seen from this figure, all the values are within a 95% confidence interval which is indicated by dotted lines. Three of the test specimens, marked in the figure by filled squares, did not reach their fatigue life during the test. Regression analysis gives the following equation which is based on 18 data sets, (n-2)= 16 degrees of freedom and a standard deviation $s = 0.3411$:

$$\log N = 11.0 - 1.01 P$$

(5)

No differences in fatigue life could be observed between the non-postcured and the postcured test specimens. This can be explained by the fact that cracks developed mainly in the couplers which are postcured by the manufacturer, so that only the crack initiation could be classified as adhesive and cohesive failure.

4.2 Acoustic emission

When crack growth occurs, one can expect that a high rate of AE activity is produced. Two AE techniques were investigated for the determination of the initiation and growth of cracks. Unfortunately, the first method which accumulated the number of AE counts versus the number of load cycles, did not indicate either crack initiation or crack propagation. This was due to the overall level of the noise while the test rig was running, which hid the AE counts caused by crack propagation. Several undertakings were accomplished to solve this problem, but without success.

Another AE technique which seems more promising, is measurement of the Felicity ratio at specific intervals during the fatigue cycling. The data shown in Figure 5 indicates that this might be a useful method for monitoring the initiation and propagation of cracks. The two test specimens referred to in Figure 5 exhibit somewhat different behaviour. The GRE-pipe tested at 5.0 MPa maintains a high Felicity ratio for a large number of cycles before a significant decrease in the ratio can be observed. The Felicity ratio of the GRE-pipe tested at 6.5 MPa drops immediately, followed by a period with only a slight decrease until the next drop in ratio occurs, and the pipe starts to leak. The two different behaviours may be explained as follows: In the pipe tested at 5.0 MPa the load is below a critical stress limit, with the consequence that a large number of load cycles must be applied before crack initiation and propagation occurs. Once a crack is initiated it propagates at a relatively high speed, and in this specific case straight through the coupler. In the second case, the applied test pressure of 6.5 MPa is sufficient for immediate initiation and propagation of a crack right from the beginning of the fatigue cycling. In this specific case, the crack follows a path at an angle of 45° to the symmetry axis of the coupler, which means that it must propagate over a longer distance compared to the crack referred to in the previous mentioned test specimen.

4.3 Damage evaluation

Composite materials exhibit very complex failure mechanisms under static and fatigue loading, because of anisotropic characteristics in their strength and stiffness. In multidirectional laminates under in-plane loading, cracks are initiated in the weakest areas and then propagate successively through stronger areas. The fatigue failure mechanisms are often divided into four basic failure mechanisms; matrix cracking, delamination, fibre breakage and interfacial disbonding, ref. [7, 8]. Any combination of these is mainly responsible for fatigue damages. The type and degree of these damages vary widely, depending upon material properties, laminations including stacking sequence, type of fatigue loading, geometry etc. All these factors makes it very difficult to predict the fatigue life of composites, and in most cases the fatigue lifetime must be determined from the results of tests performed under realistic loading conditions.

In order to characterise the damage in the GRE-pipes and joints, the test specimens were split axially for examination. The three major paths for crack propagation are illustrated by the

photographs of the split joints, Figures 6 to 8. With the exception of one test, all cracks were initiated in the adhesive between the pipe ends. The cracks then propagated either straight through the coupler, or between layers of woven roving out to the end of the coupler. The major failure mechanisms could be classified as a combination of matrix cracking and delamination. A closer examination of the coupler indicates sub-optimal laminate lay-up. The glass-fibres were not stretched out in the axial direction, with the consequence that most of the load was carried by the matrix material.

In some cases it was observed that the crack started to develop in the coupler, and then continued in air pockets in the adhesive bond line. At the end of the air entrapment the crack continued to grow in the coupler.

With the exception of one test specimen, no leakages were detected in the pipe walls, although the internal surfaces contained several cracks. These cracks were mainly located in the transition zone between the pipe and coupler, where bending moments are at play due to changes in the moment of inertia. Here, there is also a weakening of material strength due to a reduction in pipe wall thickness in order to fit the coupler (notch effects).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The present investigation was undertaken in order to supplement the current picture of the fatigue mechanisms of water hammer on filament-wound GRE-pipes, and a new test method simulating fatigue caused by water hammer in jointed filament-wound GRE-pipes has been developed. By calculating parameters for typical loading cycles during water hammer, similar loading conditions can be introduced into test specimens, so that fatigue data can be established.

The test programme has indicated that the adhesive bonded coupler joint is weaker than the GRE-pipe itself. Unless the bond line contains serious defects such as air entrapments etc., the fatigue crack will propagate through the coupler and cause leakage. In addition, micro cracks will be severe, and crack growth will occur in the external transition zone between the pipe and the coupler, due to local bending moments in this area. The accomplished tests also demonstrated that only small leakages will occur without catastrophic failure, at the applied loading conditions described in this paper.

Acoustic emission showed promising results as a method for monitoring damage growth in GRE-piping systems. The initiation and growth of cracks seems to coincide with a major decrease in the Felicity ratio, and the method could therefore be used for determining the life expectancy for GRE-pipes and fittings based on the number of cycles to crack initiation.

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Table 1: Data for the test specimens

	GRE-pipe	Coupler
Inner diameter (mm)	100.0	100.0 (bore opening) 106.5 (inner wall) 111.5
Outer diameter (mm)	106.4	
Wall thickness/Reinforcement:		
liner (mm)	0.5/Carbon surface veil	0.5/C-glass surface veil
structural wall (mm)	2.4/E-glass, roving	5.0/E-glass, woven roving
topcoat (mm)	0.3/-	0.3/-
Length (mm)	300 each	91
Fibre content (%w)	> 65	> 60
Resin & Adhesive	Bis-phenol A epoxy	Bis-phenol A epoxy
Curing agent	Aromatic amine	Aromatic amine
Fibre orientation	$\pm 55^\circ$	0/90°
Operating pressure (MPa)	2.5	2.5
Axial tensile modulus, E_a (GPa)	12	-
Hoop tensile modulus, E_t (GPa)	20.5	-
Poissons ratio, hoop/axial, ν_{at}	0.38	-
Poissons ratio, axial/hoop, ν_a	0.65	-
Production method	Filament winding	Winding

Figure 1: Illustration of two GRE-pipes jointed by an adhesive bonded coupler.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the water hammer fatigue test rig.

Figure 3: Plot of pressure versus time for one load cycle. The load signal from the INSTRON is plotted as discrete points, while the signal from the Kistler pressure transducer is presented as a curve. Both signals were recorded using a data acquisition module attached to a PC.

Figure 4: P-N diagram for the test specimens. The equation from the regression analysis is shown as a solid line analysis, while the confidence interval is indicated by the dotted lines. Filled squares represents test specimens that did not reach their fatigue life during the test.

Figure 5. Felicity ratio for two test specimens showing the difference in acoustic emission behavior.

Figure 6: Photograph of a split joint. The crack has propagated straight through the coupler.

Figure 7: Photograph of a split joint. The crack has propagated through the coupler at an angle of 45° to the symmetry axis.

Figure 8: Photograph of a split joint. The crack has propagated in air pockets in the adhesive bond line. At the end of the air entrappings, the crack has continued to grow in the coupler.